

BEYOND REACH: UNCOVERING BARRIERS TO HEALTHCARE ACCESS AMONG THE MARGINALIZED POPULATION OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This study explored the complex socio-cultural, economic, and institutional barriers that restricted healthcare access for marginalized rural women—particularly pregnant and lactating women—in the districts of Mardan and Swabi, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. A qualitative research design was adopted, and purposive sampling was used to conduct in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and key informant interviews with rural women, healthcare providers, and NGO representatives. Data were analyzed thematically using NVivo software, which revealed three overarching categories of barriers: socio-cultural constraints such as patriarchal norms, mobility restrictions, and traditional beliefs; economic hardships including hidden healthcare costs and the prioritization of household needs over maternal care; and institutional challenges such as staff shortages, absenteeism, and poor infrastructure in public health facilities. The findings demonstrated how intersecting layers of gender, poverty, and geographic isolation created a cycle of neglect and delay in accessing maternal healthcare services. The study recommended culturally sensitive community engagement, financial support mechanisms, improved transport infrastructure, recruitment of female health workers, and community-level accountability systems to enhance equitable access. These multi-faceted interventions were deemed essential for dismantling systemic exclusions and promoting maternal health equity in rural Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Maternal mortality remains a critical public health challenge in Pakistan, particularly within rural regions where structural and socio-cultural disparities persist despite gradual progress. The Pakistan Maternal Mortality Survey (PMMS, 2019) reported a national maternal mortality ratio (MMR) of 186 deaths per 100,000 live births, marking a 33% decline from 276 in 2006–07 but remaining more

than double the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) target of 70 per 100,000 by 2030 (National Institute of Population Studies [NIPS], 2020; Shaeen et al., 2022). Although rural-urban gaps have narrowed, rural women continue to bear a disproportionate burden, with an MMR of 185 compared to 157 per 100,000 in urban settings (NIPS, 2020). Provincial disparities further illustrate

this inequity: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) recorded an MMR of 165, compared to 157 in Punjab, 224 in Sindh, and 298 in Balochistan (United Nations Population Fund [UNFPA], 2022; NIPS, 2020). These figures highlight persistent structural vulnerabilities, particularly in rural KPK, where health infrastructure gaps intersect with socio-cultural constraints to exacerbate maternal health outcomes.

Despite the overall decline in maternal mortality, access to essential maternal healthcare services remains deeply inequitable across Pakistan. Analysis of the Pakistan Demographic and Health Survey (PDHS) 2017–18 indicates that only 12% of women received the full maternal care continuum, defined as eight or more antenatal visits, skilled birth attendance, and timely postnatal care (Rahman et al., 2023). Utilization of individual services is similarly limited: only 52% of women attended four or more antenatal visits, 69% delivered with skilled assistance, and just 62% received postnatal care within 48 hours (Rahman et al., 2023). These disparities are pronounced in rural areas, where institutional delivery rates remain around 40% and skilled birth attendance approximately 56%, compared to more than 75% in urban settings (Iqbal et al., 2021; Sadia et al., 2022). Socioeconomic inequality and limited female education strongly correlate with these gaps, with rural KPK exhibiting some of the lowest indicators nationwide. Census data show female literacy in KPK at 37.2% compared to 64.6% for males, and in several rural districts—including Mardan and Swabi—female literacy often falls below 36% (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics [PBS], 2023; Naz et al., 2023a).

Beyond structural and economic constraints, socio-cultural determinants are a critical dimension of maternal healthcare inequities. Evidence demonstrates that patriarchal household structures and gendered decision-making norms systematically limit women's autonomy in seeking antenatal and delivery care, frequently deferring critical decisions to male relatives or senior female members (Naz et al., 2022; Sarfraz et al., 2016). In rural KPK, Naz et al. (2023b) documented that purdah-related mobility restrictions and entrenched reliance on Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) perpetuate home deliveries in unhygienic conditions, contributing to

preventable maternal morbidity and mortality. Comparable patterns are reported in rural Punjab and Sindh, where cultural trust in TBAs and spiritual healers delay biomedical interventions and substitutes facility-based delivery, even during obstetric complications (Sadia et al., 2022; Sarfraz et al., 2016). These socio-cultural constraints, combined with poverty and weak infrastructure, reflect the first “delay” in the Thaddeus and Maine framework—the delay in deciding to seek care—which has been shown to exacerbate adverse maternal outcomes in rural Pakistan (Naz et al., 2023a; Midhet et al., 2025).

While maternal health inequities in Pakistan have been extensively documented, there remains a paucity of localized analyses that explore how socio-cultural, economic, and institutional factors intersect to shape maternal healthcare access in rural Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Existing research is dominated by national-level surveys (Aftab et al., 2023; Midhet et al., 2025) or focuses on individual determinants in isolation (Naz et al., 2022; Sarfraz et al., 2016), leaving a gap in understanding the lived realities of marginalized women in specific rural districts. This study addresses that gap by examining Mardan and Swabi, where patriarchal norms, geographic isolation, and economic precarity converge to produce unique barriers to care. Through a multi-dimensional lens, it contributes context-specific insights critical for designing culturally grounded interventions and advancing the discourse on maternal health equity in low- and middle-income rural settings.

Research Methods

Research Design and Study Site

The study adopted a qualitative research design to deeply explore the socio-cultural, economic, and institutional barriers affecting access to healthcare services among marginalized rural women, specifically pregnant and lactating women—in the districts of Mardan and Swabi, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Qualitative research design has been largely used in the literature (Riaz et al., 2024a; Riaz et al., 2024b). These districts were chosen for their blend of peri-urban and rural characteristics, allowing for a nuanced understanding of healthcare disparities shaped by cultural, structural, and economic contexts. The study focused on pregnant

and lactating women residing in rural areas, who experience layered marginalization due to gender, poverty, and geographic isolation.

Study Population and Sampling

A purposive sampling technique was used to select participants who had recently sought—or attempted to seek—maternal healthcare services from Basic Health Units (BHUs), Rural Health Centers (RHCs), and government hospitals. To incorporate institutional viewpoints, key informants such as Lady Health Workers (LHWs), midwives, and health officials were also included.

Data Collection Methods

Data were gathered using semi-structured in-depth interviews (IDIs) and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) to obtain a comprehensive picture of women lived experiences and contextual realities. A total of 10–15 in-depth interviews were conducted with individual rural women from diverse union councils in both districts. 4–6 FGDs (2–3 in each district) were conducted with groups of women to explore collective perceptions, challenges, and coping strategies. Additionally, 6–8 Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) were conducted with healthcare providers and local NGO representatives to understand systemic challenges and service delivery limitations. The interviews and FGDs revolved around themes such as traditional beliefs, mobility restrictions, decision-making dynamics, financial constraints, and perceived quality of care at government health facilities.

Data Analysis

All interviews and discussions were **audio-recorded (with consent)**, transcribed verbatim, and analyzed using thematic analysis (Naz et al., 2024b; Naz et al., 2024c). Transcripts were coded using NVivo software, where recurring patterns were identified and grouped under three major thematic areas: Socio-cultural barriers, Economic barriers and Institutional barriers. **Both** inductive and deductive coding approaches were employed to ensure a balance between emerging narratives from the field and the study's predefined research objectives.

Ethical Considerations

Strict ethical protocols were followed throughout the study. **Verbal and written informed consent** were obtained from all participants. Participants were assured of anonymity and confidentiality and were informed of their right to withdraw at any point. Ethical approval was secured from a recognized institutional review board prior to the commencement of fieldwork.

Results

3.1 Socio-Cultural Barriers

3.1.1 Patriarchal Decision-Making

One of the most significant barriers to healthcare access among the marginalized population—specifically pregnant and lactating women—in rural areas of Mardan and Swabi is the prevailing patriarchal system. Within these communities, healthcare decisions are rarely made by women themselves. Instead, male family members, especially husbands, and in some cases, elder males such as fathers-in-law or brothers-in-law, hold the authority to decide if, when, and where a woman may seek medical attention.

This male-dominated decision-making structure deeply limits women's autonomy and delays timely access to maternal healthcare services. Even when women experience pain or signs of complications, they are often required to wait for male permission or accompaniment to visit a healthcare facility.

"In my family, my husband decides where I should go for treatment. I cannot go to the clinic without his approval. Last time, I had to wait two weeks before he agreed to take me for a check-up because he was busy." (Participant 4: FGD, Mardan)

This phenomenon was also echoed by healthcare providers and community workers during key informant interviews. They highlighted how patriarchal norms result in women being treated as passive recipients rather than active participants in their own healthcare.

"In many villages, even if the woman is in pain, she needs permission from her husband. We often have to convince the men that treatment is necessary." (LHV, KII 2, Swabi)

In Swabi, the influence of extended family members—particularly mothers-in-law—further restricts women's ability to seek timely medical care.

Decisions around maternal health are sometimes deferred or dismissed by elder female relatives, who themselves are shaped by long-standing patriarchal norms.

"Sometimes, I don't feel I have the right to even suggest going to the doctor. My mother-in-law always says, 'You can wait, it's not serious.' There's no choice but to listen to her." (Participant 7: IDI, Swabi)

Many women expressed that asserting their health needs or independently visiting a health facility could lead to arguments or accusations of disobedience. The fear of being scolded or stigmatized for being "too forward" or "demanding" discourages them from even voicing their concerns.

"I know I should go to the doctor when I feel pain, but my husband always says, 'It's nothing serious,

3.1.2 Cultural Taboos and Misconceptions

Deep-rooted cultural beliefs and taboos surrounding pregnancy, childbirth, and postpartum care emerged as prominent barriers affecting healthcare access among the marginalized population in the rural areas of Mardan and Swabi. These cultural misconceptions often discourage the utilization of formal health services, especially among pregnant and lactating women, who are considered vulnerable and thus confined within traditional, home-based care systems.

A recurring belief shared across focus group discussions was the perception that pregnancy is a "natural process" that does not require medical supervision unless complications become visible. Many participants believed that frequent visits to healthcare centers were unnecessary or even harmful. **"Our elders say pregnancy is not a disease, so why go to the doctor unless something is really wrong?"** (Participant 2: FGD, Swabi)

There were also misconceptions about certain medical practices. For instance, some women expressed fear of ultrasound or antenatal procedures due to rumors and hearsay.

"They say too many ultrasounds can harm the baby, so I didn't go after the first visit. My sister-in-law even scolded me for going once without telling anyone." (Participant 6: IDI, Mardan)

Traditional practices are often prioritized over evidence-based medical care. In several interviews,

just rest for a few days.' I don't argue because I'm afraid it will cause tension in the house." (Participant 2: IDI, Swabi)

"I don't know how to talk to the doctor if I go alone. I always wait for my husband to take me because I don't want to be judged or scolded for going by myself." (Participant 3: FGD, Mardan)

These lived realities illustrate how deeply entrenched patriarchal norms restrict not only physical mobility but also the psychological confidence of marginalized women to seek healthcare independently. This gendered power imbalance must be addressed through community engagement, awareness campaigns, and empowering local women leaders and healthcare providers to foster a shift in decision-making dynamics.

Women shared that they were advised to rely on local herbal remedies or the guidance of traditional birth attendants (dais), particularly during the early stages of pregnancy.

"My mother-in-law gave me some herbs when I was feeling dizzy. She said it happens with every woman and there's no need to go to the doctor for small things." (Participant 5: IDI, Swabi)

Key informants, particularly healthcare providers, expressed concern over the persistence of myths that influence women's behaviors. They emphasized that these misconceptions are not only culturally endorsed but also reinforced by older generations of women within the household.

"Many women come to us only when things get worse. Some believe injections or medicines can lead to miscarriage, so they avoid us altogether during the early months." (Lady Health Supervisor, KII, Mardan)

These cultural taboos and misconceptions also contribute to stigma around discussing reproductive health openly, even with female health workers. In group discussions, some women admitted that they felt shy or ashamed to talk about issues like vaginal discharge, breastfeeding pain, or prenatal bleeding.

"We don't talk about these things even with other women. I feel embarrassed to say anything about my body problems in front of others." (Participant 3: FGD, Mardan)

In both Mardan and Swabi, the intergenerational transfer of traditional knowledge though well-intentioned, often reinforces barriers to modern healthcare. These belief systems, deeply embedded in the socio-cultural fabric of rural communities, undermine preventive care and delay critical interventions during pregnancy and lactation.

3.1.3 Restrictions on Female Mobility

Restrictions on the physical mobility of women emerged as a significant socio-cultural barrier affecting the marginalized population—particularly pregnant and lactating women—in rural Mardan and Swabi. These restrictions are rooted in conservative cultural norms that prioritize purdah (female seclusion), honor, and family reputation, limiting women's freedom to travel alone or access health services without male accompaniment.

In most of the focus group discussions, participants shared that visiting health facilities—even for emergencies—required permission and escort by a male relative. Without this, women often stayed at home, sometimes missing essential antenatal or postnatal care appointments.

"I cannot go to the Basic Health Unit alone. My husband or brother-in-law has to take me. If no one is free, I just stay at home and wait." (Participant 1: FGD, Swabi)

Some women expressed frustration over this dependence, especially when the men in their families were either unavailable due to work or disinterested in taking them to a health center.

"Sometimes I feel pain, but I know my husband will say he's busy or it's not important. I cannot walk alone for 20 minutes to the clinic. It's not allowed." (Participant 5: IDI, Mardan)

Health workers interviewed during key informant interviews confirmed that these mobility constraints significantly delayed access to services. They also

noted that even when healthcare facilities are within walking distance, many women are unable to go unless accompanied by a male guardian.

Even if the BHU is nearby, most women say they need a male to go with them. Some have missed multiple appointments just because no one was available to take them." (Lady Health Visitor, KII, Swabi)

In some areas, participants highlighted the lack of female-only transport options or the unavailability of gender-sensitive service delivery environments as additional deterrents. The fear of being seen traveling alone—potentially leading to gossip or shame—further reinforced the confinement of women within their homes.

"If people see a woman walking alone in the village, they start talking. I don't want anyone to say bad things, so I stay inside unless someone takes me out." (Participant 6: FGD, Mardan)

Women also reported feeling unsafe or uncomfortable using public transport, especially during pregnancy, due to crowding and the risk of harassment, which added to their reluctance to seek timely healthcare.

"Once I had to go to the hospital by van, and there were too many men. I felt very uncomfortable and decided not to go again without my husband." (Participant 3: IDI, Swabi)

These mobility restrictions significantly affect timely maternal healthcare-seeking behavior and lead to delays in recognizing and addressing potential complications. These further compounds health risks for both mothers and their infants and underscores the importance of addressing gendered mobility barriers through community sensitization and female-friendly outreach services.

Table 1: Socio-Cultural Barriers to Healthcare Access

Barrier	Description	Supporting Excerpts
Patriarchal Decision-Making	Male family members (husbands, fathers-in-law) make health decisions; women lack autonomy.	<p>"In my family, my husband decides where I should go for treatment... I had to wait two weeks before he agreed..." (Participant 4: FGD, Mardan)</p> <p>"Even if the woman is in pain, she needs permission from her husband." (LHV, KII 2, Swabi)</p>

<p>Cultural Taboos & Misconceptions</p>	<p>Beliefs such as "pregnancy is natural," "Our elders say pregnancy is not a disease, so why go to the doctor unless something is really wrong?" (Participant 2: FGD, Swabi)</p> <p>“They say too many ultrasounds can harm the baby...” (Participant 6: IDI, Mardan)</p> <p>“My mother-in-law gave me some herbs... said there’s no need to go to the doctor for small things.” (Participant 5: IDI, Swabi)</p>
<p>Female Mobility Restrictions</p>	<p>Cultural norms restrict women from traveling alone; must be accompanied by male relative.</p> <p>“I cannot go to the Basic Health Unit alone... I</p>

3.2 Economic and Structural Barriers to Healthcare Access

3.2.1 Financial Insecurity and Cost of Healthcare

A significant number of participants reported that the **cost associated with healthcare services**, even in public hospitals, remained a major obstacle. Although many basic services are claimed to be free, hidden costs such as transport, medicines, tests, and informal fees act as deterrents for the marginalized population.

"The doctor may not charge anything, but we have to buy the medicine from outside. Even the paracetamol is not available in the BHU." (Participant 3: FGD, Mardan)

Pregnant women, particularly those from laboring families, said that they had to prioritize feeding their children or household needs over their own health expenses.

"If I ask my husband for money to visit the hospital, he says, 'First let's buy flour and oil. Your health can wait.'" (Participant 1: IDI, Swabi)

KIIs revealed that public health facilities often lacked the necessary equipment or medicines, pushing families toward private facilities, which they could not afford.

"Even for a basic ultrasound, women are sent to private labs. That alone costs them Rs. 500 or more—too much for daily wage families."(Health Facility Administrator, KII, Mardan)

3.2.2 Poor Infrastructure and Distance to Facilities

Many rural women reported difficulty accessing healthcare due to **long distances** to health centers and **lack of transportation options**. Roads in remote

areas were either non-motorable or dangerous, particularly at night or during emergencies.

"The hospital is far and there's no bus in our village. We need to hire a rickshaw or wait for someone to take us on a motorbike." (Participant 2: FGD, Swabi)

Some families were delayed seeking care altogether due to the **unpredictability of transport availability**.

"When I had pain at night, there was no one to take me. The road is too bad, and no one wants to drive here in the dark." (Participant 4: IDI, Mardan)

KIIs pointed out that many Basic Health Units (BHUs) in the region are under-resourced and poorly maintained. Moreover, referral systems between BHUs and larger hospitals are either non-functional or unaffordable.

"We don't have ambulances in most rural areas, and people don't trust the referral process. They would rather stay home than risk being turned away at a tertiary hospital."(Lady Health Supervisor, KII, Swabi).

3.2.3 Inadequate Staffing and Overburdened Health Facilities

Participants across all data sources highlighted that even when they manage to reach a facility, they often face **long waiting hours, absent doctors, or rushed consultations**. The marginalized population, especially poor rural women, feel they are treated with less respect or urgency.

"There are too many patients and only one doctor. They don't even look at us properly. Sometimes they send us back saying, 'Come tomorrow.'"(Participant 5: FGD, Mardan)

In IDIs, some women shared that they spent hours waiting only to be told the female doctor was not available or that the facility had closed early.

"I went at 11 AM and waited until 3 PM. Then they said the lady doctor had left. I went back home crying." (Participant 2: IDI, Swabi)

Health officials confirmed that staffing issues, poor HR policies, and absenteeism are chronic issues.

"Rural health centers struggle to retain qualified staff. Many doctors don't want to work in villages. They mark attendance and then leave early." (District Health Official, KII, Mardan)

Table 2: Economic Barriers to Healthcare Access

Barrier	Description	Supporting Excerpts
Financial Insecurity	Hidden costs for medicines, tests, and transport despite healthcare services.	"The doctor may not charge anything, but we have to buy the medicine from outside." (Participant 3: FGD, Mardan)
Poverty vs. Maternal Prioritization	Household necessities prioritized over maternal care expenses.	"If I ask my husband for money to visit the hospital, he says, 'First let's buy flour and oil. Your health can wait.'" (Participant 1: IDI, Swabi)
Poor Transport & Long Distances	Villages lack public transport; bad roads limit emergency access.	"The hospital is far and there's no bus in our village." (Participant 2: FGD, Swabi) "When I had pain at night, there was no one to take me. The road is too bad, and no one wants to drive here in the dark." (Participant 4: IDI, Mardan)

3.3 Institutional Barriers

This theme focuses on structural and systemic challenges within healthcare facilities and service delivery systems that limit access for marginalized populations, particularly rural women. These barriers are not just logistical but reflect deeper institutional weaknesses in the rural health infrastructure.

3.3.1 Limited Availability of Female Healthcare Providers

A consistent concern across both districts was the shortage of female doctors especially in Basic Health Units (BHUs) and Rural Health Centers (RHCs). Given the cultural sensitivity around being examined by male doctors, this scarcity often led to either the complete avoidance of care or long travel to distant facilities.

"In our area, there is no female doctor. If we go to the health unit, there's always a man, and my husband won't allow that." (FGD participant, Mardan)

"The female staff comes only on some days. If you go on the wrong day, you return without a check-up. Then you wait another week." (IDI, Swabi)

"Sometimes, we refer women to district hospitals just because we have no trained midwife present at the BHU. The system does not support round-the-clock female presence." (KII, Healthcare provider, Mardan)

This shortage led to delays in antenatal and postnatal checkups and increased home births without skilled attendants, raising serious concerns about maternal and infant mortality.

3.3.2 Overburdened and Under-resourced Facilities

Many rural health units lacked basic equipment, regular medicines, and adequate staffing, making it difficult to offer quality care. Women from marginalized communities, already hesitant due to social and financial constraints, were further discouraged by the poor condition of the facilities.

“There was no ultrasound machine or even paracetamol when I visited. They told me to go to the city hospital, but I had no money for that.” (IDI, Swabi)

“They give dates for delivery check-ups, but often there are no doctors on duty. So we go to private clinics, which cost too much.” (FGD, Mardan)

“The health center is open, but there is no one inside. The nurse comes late or sometimes not at all.” (FGD, Swabi)

This results in a lack of trust in public healthcare services and pushes women toward expensive or unsafe alternatives such as home remedies, spiritual healers, or untrained traditional birth attendants.

3.3.3 Poor Referral and Follow-Up Systems

Participants and key informants noted the inefficiency of referral systems between lower- and higher-tier facilities. Once a woman was referred, no follow-up was ensured, and transportation was not facilitated. This often meant the end of the care-seeking journey.

“They referred me to the hospital in Swabi city but gave no help or ambulance. I didn’t go. I just stayed home.” (IDI, Swabi)

“If a woman is sent to a bigger hospital, there’s no record kept, or follow-up done. We don’t know what happens next.” (KII, Health Technician, Mardan)

3.3.4 Inadequate Health Education and Outreach

There was also a lack of effective health communication. Lady Health Workers (LHWs), where available, did not regularly visit or educate women about their rights or available services.

“I didn’t even know I had to go for checkups during pregnancy. No one came to tell us.” (FGD, Mardan)

“In our village, the health worker comes only during polio days. Otherwise, we don’t see her.” (IDI, Swabi)

This absence of consistent outreach limits awareness, resulting in low antenatal care uptake, missed vaccinations, and unmonitored pregnancies.

Table 3: Institutional Barriers to Healthcare Access

Barrier	Description	Supporting Excerpts
Shortage of Female Health Providers	Women avoid visiting clinics due to unavailability of female doctors.	“In our area, there is no female doctor... my husband won’t allow [a male doctor].” (FGD participant, Mardan)
Staff Absenteeism & Rushed Care	Doctors are often absent or leave early; patients face long waits or denial of services.	“Sometimes they send us back saying, ‘Come tomorrow.’” (Participant 5: FGD, Mardan) “I waited until 3 PM. Then they said the lady doctor had left.” (Participant 2: IDI, Swabi)
Under-Resourced Facilities	Lack of basic equipment, medicines, and staff in rural BHUs and RHCs.	“There was no ultrasound machine or even paracetamol...” (IDI, Swabi)
Poor Referral Systems	No transport, guidance, or follow-up after referral to higher-tier hospitals.	“They referred me to the hospital in Swabi city, but gave no help or ambulance. I didn’t go.” (IDI, Swabi)
Inadequate Health Outreach	Lady Health Workers are inconsistent or absent; women uninformed about antenatal/postnatal care.	“I didn’t even know I had to go for checkups during pregnancy. No one came to tell us.” (FGD, Mardan) “In our village, the health worker comes only during polio days. Otherwise, we don’t see her.” (IDI, Swabi)

Discussion

The present study revealed a complex interplay of socio-cultural, economic, and institutional barriers that significantly impeded access to maternal healthcare among marginalized rural women in the districts of Mardan and Swabi, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. These findings aligned with existing literature that highlighted how structural inequalities, gender norms, and systemic healthcare deficiencies jointly influenced health-seeking behavior in rural Pakistan and comparable contexts. The findings of this study revealed that patriarchal decision-making remained a fundamental barrier to maternal healthcare access among rural women in Mardan and Swabi. Women's reproductive health decisions were predominantly governed by male household members—typically husbands, fathers-in-law, or brothers-in-law—who exercised authority over the timing, location, and even the necessity of seeking medical attention. This form of patriarchal control significantly constrained women's agency and delayed critical care, thereby increasing the likelihood of maternal morbidity and mortality. These findings are consistent with Mumtaz and Salway (2007), who documented that women in rural Pakistan were often regarded as passive recipients of healthcare, with male gatekeeping delaying or obstructing timely service utilization. More recent research has also affirmed that patriarchal household structures limit women's access to maternal health services and reinforce dependency, particularly in low-income rural settings (Mukhtar, 2023; Asif et al., 2021).

The study also identified a range of cultural taboos and misconceptions surrounding pregnancy and childbirth. Many participants believed that pregnancy constituted a natural condition that did not require formal medical intervention unless visible complications arose. Misunderstandings about routine procedures, such as ultrasound scans, were widespread; these were often perceived as potentially harmful to the fetus or as mechanisms for gender detection and selective abortion, which discouraged their use. These views were typically reinforced by elder female relatives, including mothers-in-law, who held significant cultural authority in household health decisions. Such misconceptions have been similarly documented in other regions of Pakistan,

where traditional health beliefs are often prioritized over biomedical knowledge, contributing to delayed or insufficient antenatal care (Ali et al., 2021; Qureshi et al., 2020).

Furthermore, mobility restrictions emerged as a critical socio-cultural constraint. Women were generally prohibited from traveling alone to health facilities due to prevailing purdah norms and community expectations regarding modesty and family honor. Even in emergencies, they were often required to wait for a male escort, leading to further delays in accessing necessary care. This form of restricted physical autonomy not only inhibited timely healthcare-seeking behavior but also fostered psychological dependence and diminished self-efficacy. These observations align with findings from Mumtaz and Salway (2007) and were corroborated by more recent studies that emphasize how gendered social norms in rural Pakistan circumscribe women's spatial mobility and thereby restrict access to even proximate healthcare facilities (Webb & Renzaho, 2023).

Collectively, these socio-cultural barriers like patriarchal control, cultural misconceptions, and mobility restrictions formed a deeply embedded web of disadvantages that limited women's access to maternal healthcare. Addressing such challenges requires culturally sensitive interventions that go beyond infrastructure improvements and include gender-transformative strategies, community education, and the empowerment of women as autonomous healthcare users.

Economic constraints further compounded healthcare inaccessibility in the study area. Although public health services were ostensibly free, respondents consistently reported that hidden costs including medication, diagnostic tests, informal fees, and transportation represented significant financial burdens. One study highlighted the clinical and economic impact of such medicine shortages on rural patients, noting that these shortages compelled individuals to adopt risk-prone behaviors, including out-of-pocket purchases, to avoid treatment disruptions (Ali et al., 2021). In this study, participants specifically emphasized that even basic medications, such as paracetamol, were often unavailable at Basic Health Units (BHUs), forcing

them to procure these from private pharmacies at their own cost.

Households frequently prioritized fundamental survival needs such as food and shelter over maternal healthcare, creating a clear trade-off. These decisions mirrored intra-household bargaining frameworks, in which resource constraints and patriarchal norms led to the subjugation of women's health needs to collective economic priorities (Kabeer, 1994). Moreover, logistical barriers—including limited or non-existent transport, poor road quality, and absence of emergency services in remote villages—further exacerbated the situation. Such challenges reinforced the delay phenomena described in the "three delays" model, encompassing delays in decision to seek care, reaching care, and obtaining adequate care (Thaddeus & Maine, 1994).

Qualitative evidence from Pakistan and comparable settings confirmed that rural women often remained partially served or entirely excluded from formal healthcare systems due to intersecting economic and logistical constraints (Naz et al., 2023). As a result, reliance on home-based remedies, unqualified birth attendants, or informal advice from elder women was common and was not a matter of preference, but of constrained circumstances.

Institutional deficiencies in healthcare infrastructure, staffing, and service delivery further restricted access to maternal care. A pronounced shortage of female healthcare providers, particularly doctors and midwives in BHUs and Rural Health Centers (RHCs), discouraged women from seeking services due to socio-cultural sensitivity around being examined by male practitioners. Respondents consistently emphasized that their husbands and families did not permit them to consult male doctors, a finding that reiterated observations made by Shaikh and Hatcher (2005) in similar rural contexts.

Moreover, participants described frequent staff absenteeism, long waiting times, and rushed consultations, which undermined their trust in public healthcare facilities. In many cases, women arrived at clinics only to discover that the female doctor was unavailable or had left early. Health officials interviewed during the study corroborated these accounts, noting that staff shortages and weak

human resource management were persistent issues in rural health centers.

The study also uncovered weak referral systems between primary-level health units and secondary or tertiary care hospitals. Women who were referred to district hospitals often received no support with transportation, follow-up care, or information, resulting in treatment discontinuation. These findings were consistent with systemic reviews highlighting inefficiencies in Pakistan's rural referral pathways (Nishtar et al., 2013).

Furthermore, health education and outreach activities appeared insufficient or entirely absent in several communities. Respondents reported that Lady Health Workers (LHWs) were either irregular in their visits or confined their activities to immunization campaigns. As a result, many women were unaware of the need for antenatal visits, postpartum monitoring, or early danger signs. This lack of consistent engagement with community-based health services limited preventive care uptake and contributed to delayed health-seeking behavior.

In summary, the study illustrated that maternal healthcare access in rural Khyber Pakhtunkhwa was constrained by intersecting and mutually reinforcing barriers. Socio-cultural norms disempowered women and suppressed their agency; economic precarity forced difficult trade-offs between health and survival; and institutional failures eroded confidence in the public healthcare system. These findings underscored the necessity for multi-dimensional interventions that address not only physical infrastructure and medical resources but also community norms, gender dynamics, and system-level accountability.

Conclusion

The findings from this study underscore the multifaceted and deeply entrenched barriers that hinder healthcare access for marginalized populations, particularly pregnant and lactating women, in rural Khyber Pakhtunkhwa of Pakistan. Socio-cultural factors, such as patriarchal decision-making, cultural taboos, and restrictions on female mobility, consistently limit women's autonomy and delay their access to essential maternal health services. These norms not only constrain physical movement but also suppress women's confidence

and voice in asserting their health needs, often rendering them passive recipients in their own care. Economic hardships further exacerbate these challenges. Despite the presence of public health facilities, hidden costs such as transportation, diagnostic tests, and medication often place a heavy financial burden on low-income households. As a result, maternal health is frequently deprioritized in favor of other basic household needs. Structural limitations, including poor road infrastructure, lack of reliable transport, and long distances to healthcare facilities make timely medical attention difficult, particularly during emergencies or at night.

Institutional barriers such as inadequate staffing, absenteeism of female healthcare providers, and overburdened facilities contribute to a lack of trust and satisfaction with the healthcare system. Marginalized women often encounter long waiting times, dismissive treatment, and insufficient attention to their specific needs, leading to reduced motivation to seek care. The absence of functional referral systems and limited outreach programs further restricts access to quality maternal health services in remote areas.

Collectively, these barriers create a cycle of delay, neglect, and risk for rural women and their newborns. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-pronged approach involving gender-sensitive community mobilization, improved healthcare infrastructure, stronger institutional accountability, and policies that center women's agencies, dignity, and equitable access to care. Only by dismantling these interconnected layers of exclusion can meaningful progress be made toward achieving maternal health equity in rural Pakistan.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made in the light of the findings of study.

1. In KP's culturally conservative society, collaborate with **religious scholars (ulema)**, **tribal elders**, and **male Jirga members** to promote maternal health as an Islamic and communal responsibility, encouraging families to prioritize women's health and autonomy.
2. Introduce conditional cash transfers, vouchers, or interest-free loans through

- partnerships with NGOs and microfinance institutions to help low-income families afford care, transport, and nutrition.
3. Invest in road development and establish emergency transport services (e.g., community ambulances) to ensure timely access to healthcare, especially in remote areas.
4. Recruit and retain female healthcare providers (LHVs, CMWs) in rural areas by offering incentives, housing, and professional development, alongside regular training in respectful maternity care.
5. Create **village-level maternal health oversight committees** involving **women councilors, LHW supervisors, and local CSOs** to monitor service delivery in **BHU/RHCs**, report absenteeism, and provide feedback to the **District Health Offices (DHOs)** for improved access to healthcare for marginalized populations of the study area.

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